

Gas-liquid Chromatographic Study of Molar Heats of Evaporation : Effect of Molecular Structure

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Gas-liquid chromatography, using a short copper column (2 meters long) with adequate liquid phase coating (Silicone Elastomer SE-30) provides typical conditions for separation, identification and calculation of some thermodynamic constants of various highly divergent organic compounds, including high-boiling normal alkylated benzenes, halogenated aromatic rings and chlorinated hydrocarbons. The technique also provides a means to trace the effect of molecular structure upon thermodynamic values like molar heats of evaporation. Especially important is the role of inter- and intramolecular hydrogen bondings such as molecular orientation in space and polarisabilities of molecules in specific circumstances.

GAS-liquid chromatography technique is used for the determination of molar heats of evaporation (ΔH) of some alkylbenzenes, halogenated benzenes, alcohols and chlorinated hydrocarbons on silicone elastomer SE-30 as the liquid phase (coating solvent). Most data are new and provide good information about different factors affecting the solution and evaporation of these solutes on specific surfaces other than the known effect on the boiling point of each solute.

Experimental

(a) *Setup*: A PYE Unicam GLC (Pye Series 104 Chromatograph) is used. It is equipped with a flame-ionization detector and a PM 8220 recorder.

(b) *Columns*: A copper column, (length 2 meter, i.d. 5 mm) is used. It is packed with SE-30 (15% w/w) liquid phase on Diatomite (solid support, 60-70 mesh).

(c) *Chemicals*: Aldrich and B. D. H. chemicals were used. Purity of chemicals was tested chromatographically. Each chemical gave only one peak, applying the highest recorder sensitivity.

(d) *Working parameters*:

Detector temp.	= 240°.
Hydrogen pressure	= 12.5 lb/in ² .
Air pressure	= 5 lb/in ² .
Flow rate	= 30 ml/min.
Recorder speed	= 0.5 cm/min.
Gas carrier	= Nitrogen.

These parameters were kept constant for all the experiments.

(e) *Samples*: Four systems were investigated

1. *n*-Alkylbenzenes
2. Halogenated benzenes
3. *n*-Alcohols
4. Chlorinated hydrocarbons

Chemicals composing each system were injected with the aid of a micro syringe. Sample volume was 0.15 μ l. Injections of individual compounds were also made prior to every collective run to ensure a complete resolution of peaks. No overlap between peaks was observed because of the careful selection of temperature ranges.

Calculations of ΔH : In order to calculate the molar heat of evaporation (ΔH) of each compound the retention time t_R is multiplied by the flow rate to get the retention volume V_R . This retention volume is then corrected to zero degree and per gram solvent (liquid phase) to yield the specific retention volume V_g .

$$V_g = \frac{V_R \times 273}{W_L \times K}$$

where W_L is the weight of silicone elastomer in gram¹ and K is the absolute temperature of the column.

Plots of $\log V_g$ against $10^3/K$ yielded straight line.

According to the equation $\log V_g = \frac{\Delta H}{2.3 RT} + k$, ini-

tially proposed by Littlewood *et al*² and subsequently modified by Ambrose¹, ΔH should be equal to the slope of such a plot times 2.3R (R = gas constant = 1.987 cal mole⁻¹ and k is a constant, characteristic of such an equation). In this way molar heats of evaporation of the systems were calculated. Since ΔH is constant, dependence of $\log V_g$ on $10^3/K$ should be linear according to this equation. Present results confirm this fact (Figs. 2, 4, 5).

Results and Discussion

System 1: The normal alkylbenzenes: Six normal alkylbenzenes, toluene, *n*-ethylbenzene, *n*-propylbenzene, *n*-butylbenzene, *n*-amylbenzene and 1-phenylhexane were studied. The chosen range of

temperatures (100-130°) produced resolutions with excellent peaks (Fig. 1) inspite of the short length of the separation column (2 meters only). Separation and identification of the heavier compounds like *n*-amylbenzene and 1-phenylhexane are of major importance both in petrochemical industries and research studies. 1-Phenylhexane is a principal constituent in diesel fuel. This compound and similar alkylbenzenes have been used as good models for investigating the intramolecular excitation energy transfer⁵ in nuclear and radiation chemistry. Owing to its relatively high boiling point (226°) and low volatility, there were some difficulties in the elution of 1-phenylhexane in gas-liquid chromatography.

Fig. 1. Dependence of log V_g on temperature. 1-Phenylhexane

$$\log V_g = \frac{\Delta H}{2.3 RT} + k$$

$$\Delta H = \text{Slope} \times 2.3R$$

$$\Delta H = 11.500 \text{ K cal/mole}$$

Retention time t_R , retention volume V_R , specific retention volume V_g , and $\log V_g$ for compounds in system 1 against varying temperature are listed in Table 1. These values decrease with increasing temperature. Retention time at the same temperature increases from toluene to 1-phenylhexane, that is with increasing number of carbon atoms (which evidently results in increasing molecular weights and increasing boiling points) (Table 2).

Molar heats of evaporation: Molar heats of evaporation, ΔH , of the six alkylbenzenes were calculated from slopes of plots similar to those given in Fig. 2. Dependence of $\log V_g$ on the reciprocal of the absolute temperature is linear since

TABLE 1

n-Propylbenzene : ($\Delta H=7.4198$ K cal/mole)					
Temp. K	1/K	t_R	V_R	V_g	$\log V_g$
373	2.68×10^{-3}	11.2	386	146.98	2.165
383	2.61×10^{-3}	9	270	114.55	2.059
388	2.57×10^{-3}	7.8	234	98.002	1.991
393	2.54×10^{-3}	7	210	86.892	1.988
398	2.51×10^{-3}	6.4	192	78.391	1.894
403	2.48×10^{-3}	5.4	162	65.322	1.815
n-Ethylbenzene : ($\Delta H=7.337$ K cal/mole)					
		7.2	216	94.101	1.973
		5.8	174	73.825	1.868
		5.0	150	62.822	1.798
		4.6	138	57.061	1.756
		4.4	132	53.894	1.731
		3.4	102	41.129	1.614
Toluene : ($\Delta H=5.474$ K cal/mole)					
		4	120	52.278	1.718
		3.8	114	48.36	1.684
		3.2	96	40.206	1.604
		3	90	37.213	1.570
		3	90	36.746	1.565
		2.2	66	26.610	1.425
1-Phenylhexane ($\Delta H=11.500$ K cal/mole)					
		69	2070	901.809	2.955
		48.8	1464	621.14	2.793
		41	1230	515.141	2.711
		34	1020	421.755	2.625
		29.2	876	357.666	2.553
		24	720	290.322	2.462
Amylbenzene : ($\Delta H=10.2442$ K cal/mole)					
		37.4	1122	488.806	2.689
		27	810	348.666	2.536
		23.6	708	296.52	2.472
		20	600	243.75	2.3874
		17.2	516	210.678	2.323
		14.4	432	174.193	2.241
n-Butylbenzene : ($\Delta H=9.0068$ K cal/mole)					
		21	630	274.463	2.438
		15.8	474	201.108	2.303
		13.4	402	168.363	2.226
		12	360	148.854	2.172
		10.4	312	127.386	2.105
		8.8	264	106.451	2.027

TABLE 2

System 1: Alkylbenzenes
Temperature = 373 K

Compound	M.W.	b.p. °C	t_R	V_R	V_g	$\log V_g$
Toluene	92	110	4	120	52.278	1.718
n-Ethylbenzene	106	135	7.2	216	94.101	1.973
n-Propylbenzene	120	159	11.2	386	146.90	2.165
n-Butylbenzene	134	183	21	630	274.463	2.438
n-Amylbenzene	148	204	37.4	1122	488.806	2.689
n-Phenylhexane	162	226	69	2070	901.809	2.955

the molar heat of evaporation is constant. Deviation from linearity reflects a variation in density of the compound under investigation with temperature. This was observed in the case of toluene (b.p. = 110°) where 4 out of 6 experiments were done at temperatures higher than its boiling point and considerable fluctuations were observed (Table 1). Lowering temperature ranges deteriorated the whole situation where heavier members did not elute at all.

Fig. 2. Chromatogram of a mixture of *n*-alkylbenzenes. Separation from column containing 15% SE-30 on Diatomite.
System 1 : Alkylbenzenes column temp. : 190° ; Flow rate = 30 ml/min

Molar heats of evaporations for system 1 are listed in Table 3 and plotted in Fig. 3 against the number of carbon atoms in the side chain (the alkyl group). They show linear dependence. The explanation for this lies in the structure of these successive *normal* alkylbenzenes. There is a constant difference of 14 units of mass (mass of CH_2 group) between any two successive compounds. The corresponding boiling points also have almost constant difference (21-25°) (see Table 3).

System 2 : Halogenated benzenes : Four compounds viz. fluoro-, chloro-, bromo- and iodo-benzenes were studied to investigate the effect of the different halogen atoms, attached to the benzene ring upon molar heat of evaporation of these compounds.

In cases of these compounds also, the values of t_R and $\log V_e$ decrease with increasing tempera-

TABLE 3

System 1 : Alkylbenzenes				
Compound	M.W.	b.p. °C	No of carbon atoms in the side chain	ΔH K cal/mole
Toluene	92	110	1	5.474
<i>n</i> -Ethylbenzene	106	135	2	7.337
<i>n</i> -Propylbenzene	120	159	3	7.4198
<i>n</i> -Butylbenzene	134	183	4	9.0068
<i>n</i> -Amylbenzene	148	204	5	10.2442
1-Phenylhexane	162	226	6	11.500

ture (Table 4). Further, t_R and $\log V_e$ as well as molar heats of evaporation increase with increasing molecular weight (and resultant increase in boiling points) of these compounds (Table 5). It is also found that the differences in values of ΔH are solely attributable to the differences in masses of the attached halogen atoms (Table 6).

Fig. 3

Fig. 4. Iodobenzene.

Compound	Temp. (K)	353	363	368	373	383	388
Fluorobenzene	t_R	4	4	3	2.8	2.6	2.6
	$\log V_g$	1.7361	1.7301	1.599	1.563	1.519	1.5141
Chlorobenzene	t_R	11	10	7.4	6.6	5.6	5.1
	$\log V_g$	2.1754	2.128	1.991	1.935	1.852	1.8067
Bromobenzene	t_R	18.5	16.8	12	10.3	8.3	7.6
	$\log V_g$	2.4012	2.353	2.201	2.129	2.033	1.9799
Iodobenzene	t_R	35	31.6	22	18.5	14.2	12.6
	$\log V_g$	2.6781	2.627	2.464	2.383	2.257	2.1945

Compound	M.W.	b.p. °C	t_R	V_R	V_g	$\log V_g$
Fluorobenzene	96	85	2.8	84	36.594	1.563
Chlorobenzene	112.5	192	6.6	198	86.258	1.935
Bromobenzene	157	156	10.3	309	134.615	2.129
Iodobenzene	204	188	18.5	555	241.785	2.3834

Compound	Mass of the attached halogen atom	ΔH, K cal/mole
Fluorobenzene	19	5.426
Chlorobenzene	35.5	8.625
Bromobenzene	80	9.20
Iodobenzene	127	10.0556

The difference in the values of molar heat of evaporation of fluorobenzene and chlorobenzene is too large, compared to the difference in ΔH values of chlorobenzene and bromobenzene or of bromobenzene and iodobenzene. Halogenated benzenes (other than the fluoro-one) have in general low boiling points but they have relatively high molar heats of evaporation as we shall see later (Table 12). All of them display small peaks compared to the peaks of other compounds. This might be the consequence of bad combustion in hydrogen. Especially important is the nature of the halogen atom attached to benzene ring. We should therefore find the explanation in the combination of a halogen atom with a single aromatic ring and the probable mutual interaction of the six π electrons in the benzene ring with the strongest electronegative atoms having the highest electron affinities among other elements in the periodic table. Fluorine, however, has its own peculiarities^{4,5}.

A comparison between system 1 and system 2 is shown in Table 7. Both of them have the aromatic ring of benzene. Fluorobenzene is an exception, having larger molecular weight and smaller boiling point than toluene.

It is interesting to note that ΔH values of chloro- and bromobenzenes are higher than ΔH values of *n*-ethyl- and *n*-propylbenzenes although the former compounds have lower boiling points (but higher molecular weights) than the latter.

More interesting is the comparison of bromobenzene with *n*-butylbenzene, where the first has a slightly larger ΔH value but a considerably smaller boiling point than the second. If it is a matter of difference in molecular weights, GLC will have to have a new outlook to explain such findings and to answer the question of how does a more volatile compound (bromobenzene) have a higher molar heat of evaporation than a less volatile compound having less ΔH value. Differences in types of interactions of solutes with the same liquid phase are able to answer such a question. If this particular column is replaced by another one having a different packing with different liquid phase, the whole picture may be reversed.

TABLE 7—COMPARISON BETWEEN VALUES OF ΔH FOR THE COMPOUNDS SYSTEMS 1 AND 2. ALL COMPOUNDS HAVE THE AROMATIC RING OF BENZENE

Compound	M.W.	b. p. °C	ΔH , K cal/mole
Toluene	92	110	5.474
<i>n</i> -Ethylbenzene	106	135	7.337
<i>n</i> -Propylbenzene	120	159	7.4198
<i>n</i> -Butylbenzene	134	183	9.0068
Fluorobenzene	96	85	5.428
Chlorobenzene	112.5	132	8.625
Bromobenzene	157	156	9.200
Iodobenzene	204	188	10.0556

System 3 : *n*-alcohols : The intermolecular hydrogen bonding effect : Four normal alcohols viz., amyl alcohol, hexanol, heptanol and octanol, were studied to examine the effect of the intermolecular hydrogen bonds on retention times of these alcohols and their molar heats of evaporation. The higher alcohols were chosen because there is no previous studies on the calculations of their molar heats of evaporation. Values of t_R and $\log V_g$ at five different temperatures are shown in Table 8. These values decrease with

TABLE 8

Compound	Temp. K $10^3/K$	System 3 : <i>n</i> -Alcohols				
		363	373	383	395	403
Amyl alcohol	t_R	4.4	3.6	3.0	2.4	2.4
	$\log V_g$	1.771	1.6725	1.5818	1.4737	1.4628
Hexanol	t_R	9.4	7.2	5.8	4.4	4.0
	$\log V_g$	2.101	1.9735	1.8682	1.7370	1.6847
Heptanol	t_R	17.6	13.0	9.6	7.2	6.0
	$\log V_g$	2.373	2.2302	2.0870	1.9509	1.8608
Octanol	t_R	34	23.2	16.8	12.2	9.4
	$\log V_g$	2.659	2.4817	2.3300	2.1799	2.0557

increasing temperature but increase with increasing molecular weights down the group. Fig. 5 illustrates the inverse dependence of $\log V_g$ for *n*-octanol on temperature. It increases with decreasing temperature. Dependence, as it is expected to be, is linear as a result of the constancy of ΔH .

Fig. 5. Octanol.

Compared to the members of system 2, these four alcohols have, in general, low molecular weights and high boiling points (Table 9). Differences between the values of ΔH are not regular. They do not reflect the successive increase in methylene group (CH_2) in the alcohols. However, the differences in any two successive boiling points are also almost constant ($18-20^\circ$).

TABLE 9

Compound	M.W.	b.p. °C	Δt	System 3 : <i>n</i> -Alcohols	
				No. of CH_2 groups	ΔH , K cal per mole
Amyl alcohol	88	138	18	4	6.7758
Hexanol	102	166	20	5	7.6686
Heptanol	116	176	18	6	9.246
Octanol	130	194	18	7	9.8026

Fig. 6. Chromatogram of a mixture of *n*-amyl alcohol, *n*-hexanol, *n*-heptanol and *n*-octanol.
 Column temp. : 100°, Flow rate : 80 ml/min, Carrier gas : Nitrogen, separation from a column
 (2 meter long) containing 15% SE-30 on Diatomite.

High boiling points of these alcohols are in fact attributed to the effect of hydrogen bonds existing between hydrogen atoms and oxygen atoms of the hydroxyl group of the neighbouring alcohol molecules. Hydrogen bondings yield intermolecular associations. These associations lower vapour pressure and consequently the volatility.

These associations and the high boiling points are not positively reflected on ΔH values (Table 9) as these values are in fact smaller than those of the four halogenated benzenes (Tables 6 and 7), excluding amyl alcohol which has a higher ΔH value than fluorobenzene.

Shapes of normal alcohols peaks : These four alcohols (especially the higher ones) have eluted with tails (Fig. 6). Raising the column temperature minimises such tails (Fig. 7). The higher the temperature the more symmetrical is the peak. There are several ways in dealing with this

problem of tailing. Best results were obtained by introducing the so-called "Tailing Reducer"^{11,6} 1.5% squalane deposited on adsorbent (Pelletex).

System 4 : Chlorinated hydrocarbons : Dichloromethane, chloroform and carbon tetrachloride were studied (Tables 10 and 11). Boiling points and molar heats of evaporation increase with increasing number of attached chlorine atoms. Members of this system have in general low boiling points and the lowest molar heats of evaporation.

Like system 2, peaks of these three compounds are very small though they are symmetrical and sharp. Whether this is due to bad combustion in hydrogen or because of an interaction between chlorine atoms and the silicone coating remains to be clarified.

Flame ionization detector has been shown not to be affected by water or carbon dioxide. This

Fig. 7. Chromatogram of a mixture of *n*-amyl alcohol, *n*-hexanol, *n*-heptanol and *n*-octanol.

Column temp. : 130°, Flow rate : 30 ml/min, Carrier gas : Nitrogen, separation from a column (2 meter long) containing 15% SE-30 on Diatomite.

TABLE 10

Compound	System 4 : CH ₂ Cl ₂ , CHCl ₃ , CCl ₄							
	Temp. K 10°/K	313	323	333	343	348	353	358
CH ₂ Cl ₂	<i>t_R</i>	2.8	2.8	2.2	1.8	1.8	2.0	1.8
	log V _g	1.6395	1.6259	1.5079	1.4070	1.401	1.4412	1.3893
CHCl ₃	<i>t_R</i>	4.6	4.6	3.6	3.0	2.8	3.0	2.6
	log V _g	1.8551	1.8415	1.7218	1.6298	1.5935	1.6173	1.5490
CCl ₄	<i>t_R</i>	7.0	6.7	5.4	4.4	4.0	4.0	3.4
	log V _g	2.0375	2.0048	1.8979	1.7961	1.7484	1.7422	1.6655

also raises the question of the effect of one, two or three chlorine atoms upon its sensitivity.

TABLE 11

System 4 : CH ₂ Cl ₂ , CHCl ₃ , CCl ₄			
Compound	M. W.	b. p. °C	ΔH, K cal/mole
CH ₂ Cl ₂	85	40	3.45
CHCl ₃	110	61	3.79
CCl ₄	154	77	5.198

It is equally probable that the large reduction in peak size is due to surface adsorption of a major part of the sample itself by inner walls of the copper column⁶.

Conclusions and general remarks :

Molar heats of evaporation for seventeen compounds were experimentally calculated using GLC technique. Of them, toluene was studied earlier^{2,7}. The following table shows different ΔH values of toluene found by different authors using different liquid phases :

	Liquid phase	ΔH, K cal/mole
Present result	SE-30	5.474
Reference 2	Silicone 702	7.9
Reference 2	Tritolylphosphate	9.0
Reference 7	Diisodecylphthalate	8.13

It is evident from this table that different liquid phases yield different ΔH values for the same compound. Smallest ΔH values of toluene correspond to the best surfaces and the easiest means for evaporation. Once evaporation as an endothermic process takes place on such surfaces by the absorption of minimum energy, such surfaces (liquid phases) should be favoured from the economic standpoint.

Silicone Elastomer-30 has proved to be an excellent coating liquid phase. Wide range chemicals of different structures were surprisingly separated and identified. Just one failure is observed. Our column was not able to resolve *m*-xylene from *p*-xylene although it did resolve the *ortho* from the *meta* and *para* isomers (Fig. 8). Lowering oven temperature did not help since *m*- and *p*-xylenes have almost the same boiling points (139 and 138° respectively).

Further experiments have shown that other isomers like *o*- and *m*-chloroanilines are separable on our column at all five temperatures chosen for this experiment.

Contrary to the case of *o*- and *m*-xylenes, the *ortho*-chloroaniline isomer eluted before the *meta* one (Fig. 9). The intramolecular hydrogen bonding existing between chlorine atom and one hydrogen atom in NH₂ group of the same molecule reduces the vapour pressure of *o*-chloroaniline to a lower extent than does the intermolecular hydrogen

Fig. 8. Chromatogram of a mixture of: toluene, *p*-xylene, *o*-xylene and bromohexane. Column temp. : 70°. Flow rate : 30 ml/min, separation from a column (2 meter long) containing 15% SE-30 on Diatomite.

bonding existing between chlorine atom of one molecule and one hydrogen atom in NH_2 group of a second molecule, giving rise to a fairly well-linked association.

o-chloroaniline :
Intramolecular hydrogen bonding

m-chloroaniline :
Intermolecular hydrogen bonding

Chloro-, bromo- and iodobenzenes, specially the first two, have in general high molar heats of evaporation with respect to their comparatively low

boiling points (Table 12). Contrary to these, normal alcohols have high boiling points but low molecular weights. It seems that the retention of

TABLE 12—MOLAR HEATS OF EVAPORATION OF SOME ORGANIC COMPOUNDS WITH DIFFERENT STRUCTURES ON SE-30 (15% W/W). NUMERICAL VALUES ARE TABULATED IN AN INCREASING ORDER

Compound	M.W.	b. p. °C	ΔH , K cal/mole
CH_2Cl_2	85	40	3.45
$CHCl_3$	119	61	3.79
CCl_4	154	77	5.1980
Fluorobenzene	96	85	5.428
Toluene	92	110	5.474
Amyl alcohol	88	138	6.7758

(Table 12 contd.)

<i>n</i> -Ethylbenzene	106	135	7.987
<i>n</i> -Propylbenzene	120	159	7.4198
<i>n</i> -Hexanol	102	166	7.6636
Chlorobenzene	112.6	132	8.626
<i>n</i> -Butylbenzene	134	183	9.0068
Bromobenzene	157	166	9.200
<i>n</i> -Heptanol	116	176	9.246
<i>n</i> -Octanol	130	194	9.8026
Iodobenzene	204	188	10.0556
<i>n</i> -Amylbenzene	148	204	10.2442
1-Phenylhexane	162	226	11.500

different compounds have little relation to their boiling points or molecular weights, but are more closely related to their polarisabilities, their abilities to form associations, and are also affected by the spatial structure of the molecules (branching, *o*-, *m*- or *para*-isomerism)¹.

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Fig. 9. Chromatogram of a mixture of: pyridine, aniline, *o*-chloroaniline, *m*-chloroaniline and dimethylaniline. Column temp.: 140°, Flow rate: 30 ml/min, Carrier gas: Nitrogen, separation from a column (2 meter long) containing 15% SE-30 on Diatomite.